

Training Pilot Operations Guide

You have worked hard to develop a training course or module you wish to try out, or pilot, for the first time. So what should be done to deliver a successful pilot, and what differs from running an established workshop? This guide aims to help you navigate the many decisions related to planning, organising and delivering a pilot workshop, so that both the learners and the training team get the most out of it.

Whilst this guide is aimed at those involved in training pilots, many aspects also apply to training in general, so may also be helpful for those running established training events.

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Planning and Preparation

In his treatise the Art of War, Sun Tzu said that "every battle is won before it's even fought", and so it is with training pilots - early preparation is key. That's certainly not to say that a pilot is a battle against learners, or if it is a battle, it's a battle with learners against barriers to knowledge, both from the perspective of the learners wanting to improve their skills, and the training team wanting to understand how the course needs to improve. But perhaps a better way to see a training pilot is as a collaboration between the instructors and the learners, where decisions related to planning aim to maximise the exchange of knowledge in both directions: from the training materials and training team to the learners, and from the learners in terms of feedback to the training team (and by extension, the training materials).

Based on this aim, the goals of a training pilot are typically twofold:

1. **For the learner:** deliver a positive learning experience for attendees that is measurable against the learning objectives for the training
2. **For the training team:** gather actionable feedback to improve the organisation, delivery, and training materials for future events (and sometimes, the same event)

The next sections will cover key decisions that need to be made to accomplish these goals, and during planning it's a good idea to capture decisions within a pilot brief. A pilot brief is a short, living document that evolves during the pre-workshop stages and forms a single agreed point of reference for those involved.

What will be Piloted?

When pilots are being planned there is often an understandable focus on the learning content and training materials that are being piloted, but it's a good idea to ensure that how it will be organised, delivered, and assessed receive equal attention.

For a group developing an entirely new course for the first time, this would obviously involve piloting many of these aspects for the first time. However for more established groups, or projects that aim to deliver multiple training events, some aspects may be reused alongside established ones, so it's a good idea to discuss and explicitly record in the pilot brief how each aspect will be handled. Examples may include some or all of the following:

- For content, it could be a whole course of new modules, new versions of existing modules, or perhaps piloting a selection of new modules that will form part of a larger course in the future. If it's the latter, it makes sense to pilot these in logical groups and orderings as much as possible, so there is a consistent learning narrative throughout the pilot.
- You might be trying out new ways of delivering an existing course, perhaps piloting an online version of one that was previously conducted in-person.
- Perhaps you're aiming to increase course attendance, so you're piloting new ways of promoting events to your target audience.

Alongside any new aspect to be piloted, ensure there are ways to assess to what extent it has been successful, and to capture how to improve it for next time. We'll cover ways of doing this later in the guide.

Where and How will it be Piloted?

Two decisions that greatly affect the shape of a pilot are how it will be delivered and whether it's held online or in-person. There are considerable differences in the options for these choices that will greatly affect the event, so the advantages and disadvantages of each should be carefully considered.

Method of Delivery

There are two delivery models, both organised around a scheduled event, we'll consider in this guide:

- **Instructor-led (pedagogical)**, where learners follow the lead of an instructor in a shared learning environment, using techniques such as presentations or live coding.
- **Supported self-learning (andragogical)**, where the responsibility and pace of learning is passed to the learner, although within an environment shared with other learners.

In both cases, helpers (or other instructors) are on hand to answer questions and help solve problems.

Although outside of the scope of this guide, at the far end of the self-learning spectrum there is also asynchronous self-learning, where learning is conducted purely in the learners' own environments and typically without direct support if problems are encountered.

	Instructor-led	Supported self-learning
Advantages		
	Well suited for novice learners who haven't built a working mental model of fundamentals yet	Well suited for intermediate or advanced learners; they typically require less direct instruction
	Greater opportunity for structured group exercises	More flexible, learners can fit it around schedules
	Since teaching is synchronised, real-time problem solving across the cohort for common problems	Easier to scale to accommodate more learners - just add more helpers
	More welcoming / less intimidating for coding novices	Progress through material at own pace
	Easier to build a rapport between students and instructors	Learners can choose their own learning path, if the course supports it
Disadvantages		
	More taxing for instructors, so may need more of them to rotate them per session	Less engaging, can prove difficult for learners to maintain motivation over many sessions, easier to be distracted
	Requires capable instructors to	Far more difficult for instructors to

instruct room at right pace and deal with problems	gauge learner progress and problems
Risk of learners falling behind if they encounter a problem	Lower knowledge sharing; less opportunities to learn from other's questions and experiences
Success greatly depends on quality of instructors	Learners can feel more isolated

For established training courses, switching to the other mode of delivery may still work well, although success depends largely on the nature of the material, an understanding of the typical challenges encountered with the material (and whether they are suited to a particular delivery style), and the technical level of the learners. Of course, for pilots, there are many more unknowns, particularly with what learners (and instructors) will find challenging, and to what extent there are undiscovered errors in the pilot materials. How problems are handled and communicated is therefore even more important.

Issues tend to surface much more quickly in instructor-led delivery, which are then resolved (with learners able to use solutions to common problems immediately). Capable instructors are also able to adapt the learning narrative in the event of unsolvable issues, using analogous examples to illustrate the same concepts. However with self-learning, as noted in their drawbacks, the self-pacing and distance learning aspects may mean that problems aren't always so readily identified and may lead to learners struggling with the material if they are unsure they are at fault. Plus, any solutions to problems must be communicated to other learners somehow, which is more challenging with a self-learning approach.

One way to make self-learning more engaging is to include pre-recorded videos of instructors in the material. This could be for course or section introductions, or for explaining fundamental or difficult concepts, although note that developing, recording, and editing course videos often takes a fair amount of effort, as does re-recording/re-editing them if the underlying material needs to change. However, if a self-learning course is planned to be developed from an existing in-person one, recording instructors' presentations for the self-learning version can mitigate this considerably.

There is also a third, hybrid model of both, where the training is initially instructor-led (for example, using live coding) then switches to supported self-learning, which has the benefit of high levels of engagement and feedback with introductory topics to give the training momentum, motivate learners, and bring them up to a baseline skill level, whilst then allowing them individual space to self-learn remaining topics at their own pace.

In-person vs Online

The rise of teleconference platforms, together with the pandemic, has seen online training events becoming increasingly popular. Let's look at online compared to in-person training.

	In-person	Online
Advantages		
	Greater social engagement between instructors and attendees - a more communal event	Easy to organise and host event
	Easier for multiple helpers to solve multiple problems simultaneously	More flexible for attendees; easier to drop in and out on own schedule
	With enough helpers, barrier to ask for help is lower for attendees	Works well for smaller pilots
	Feedback (from instructors to learners and vice versa) is often immediate	Scales very well for guided self-learning model of delivery (just add virtual rooms each with a helper)
	Typically more enjoyable for both instructors and learners	Convenient for geographically split cohorts
		Allows learners to engage via chat instead of verbally - may encourage learners who are anxious to contribute
Disadvantages		
	Greater effort (and sometimes cost) to organise and prepare venue	Typically a much higher rate of drop-offs and no-shows
	Physical travel, which may dissuade potential attendees and present a barrier to accessibility	Doesn't scale well with instructor-led training - difficult to handle multiple problems
	May exclude some attendees due to cost of travel	Harder for instructors to teach and gauge overall progress
		Harder for attendees to engage with material and instructors
		Tempting for attendees to split attention on other things and get too far behind
		Potential attendee issues with poor internet connections

May prove difficult for learners to manage instructor, materials, and own terminal/IDE on single laptop screen

There is a common theme shared with supported self-learning in terms of their disadvantages: particularly with pilots, the identification and resolution of issues is often more difficult and time-consuming, and it's harder to gauge overall progress. Online delivery together with supported self-learning may therefore prove especially challenging for both instructor and learner, so for initial pilots and inexperienced training teams an in-person instructor-led event will likely make the most sense.

However, there are ways to mitigate issues with running online + self-learning training. Organisers often take advantage of "physical" virtualisation, with events splitting the cohort into manageable groups across multiple "breakout" rooms each with an instructor (or helper) to assist learners. This helps to reduce the communication "bandwidth" and cross-talk issues with using a single virtual room, although at the expense of a greater need for coordination between instructors and helpers in separate rooms. Shared documents and backchannel communication also greatly help to record and share issues and solutions found in separate virtual rooms.

How will you Collect Feedback?

Collecting feedback is a critical aspect of ensuring the success and continuous improvement of your training workshop, and should be aligned with the goals of your pilot. It's important to clearly define what you want the pilot to achieve beforehand so that you can tailor your feedback collection to measure these specific goals. In particular, ensure you collect feedback on any aspects of your workshop that have never been trialled before.

As well as collecting feedback on the training materials, consider collecting feedback on other aspects of the workshop which affect the instructors' and learners' experiences including the method of delivery and workshop organisation. It can also be helpful to collect feedback on how participants heard about the workshop and what attracted them to it, this can help refine your marketing strategies for future events.

It's easy to focus on learner experiences and neglect the perspective of the instructors or helpers, but observations and suggestions from the teaching team may also provide valuable insights from the pilot workshop. One method of collecting feedback from instructors is to provide in-situ instructor notes, via a platform such as GoogleDocs, for instructors to capture experiences and suggestions. For a more structured method of collecting instructor feedback, you could use a specialised training platform such as Oxford's Gutenberg infrastructure, which allows instructors to add annotations/comments directly to learning material to highlight obstacles to learning or errors.

Surveys are a popular method of feedback collection. Feedback surveys can be used before the workshop to gauge participants' expectations and prior knowledge, at the end of each day to monitor ongoing satisfaction and address issues promptly, and after the workshop to assess

overall effectiveness and areas for future improvement. Ensure these surveys are concise to avoid survey fatigue and encourage honest and thorough responses.

A particularly useful tool to determine the learning effectiveness of the workshop is to establish prior knowledge and post-workshop knowledge, by asking the same technical ability questions (based on the expected learning outcomes) in the pre-workshop and post-workshop surveys. For a session teaching the Bash shell, assuming a learning outcome is to be able to write a Bash script to execute an operation over a number of files, an example question might be "Could you write a script to loop over all the files in a directory and output the first five lines of each file?", and adding this to both surveys. By developing similar key questions for each session or topic, this presents a number of benefits:

- **The pre-workshop survey establishes a prior knowledge baseline across the cohort,** allowing instructors to tailor the pilot according to cohort ability.
- **Comparing these questions' results from pre- and post-workshop surveys indicates the extent to which learning took place** across the pilot, and helps to highlight training material areas that need improvement.

The idea is to ensure that the questions are sufficiently representative of the learning outcome, but to not have too many of them.

Additionally, at the end of each day or section it can be helpful to hold wrap-up sessions to facilitate immediate and open feedback. These sessions allow participants and instructors to voice their thoughts while they are still fresh.

By implementing a comprehensive and organised feedback collection process, you can ensure you gather as much useful information as possible from your pilot workshop.

How to Develop Training Materials?

The development of training materials - and the pedagogy behind it - is a volume of guides in itself, but there are key aspects to note that help with running pilots. An established approach to lesson development, and one recommended by the Carpentries, is backwards design (also known as reverse instructional design). Using this approach, instead of starting with the topics to teach and writing content, the process starts by considering the intended learning outcomes as a set of goals (and in the case of pilots, these goals should stem from the overall goals of the pilot). The three fundamental steps to backwards design are:

- **Identify what learners should be able to do by the end of the pilot** as a set of intended learning outcomes - what should the learners be able to do at the end of the pilot?
- **Develop assessments to determine whether learning has taken place,** derived directly from the intended learning outcomes, instead of solely as part of the organisation of a pilot which is fairly typical
- **Plan lesson content that prepares learners to complete the assessment successfully,** which keeps lesson content relevant, since it's directly derived from what will be assessed, and by extension from the learning outcomes

Another advantage of this approach is that the learning outcomes are usable directly to set clear course expectations with learners, in terms of what will be taught, when advertising the workshop and introducing the course on the day.

Another key aspect are the types of learning material to use, with many workshops making use of multiple types:

Type of Material	Advantages	Disadvantages
Hosted materials online	<p>Potentially editable in real time if changes/corrections need to be made - more likely with pilots</p> <p>Since it's hosted and available centrally, easier to collaborate with others on lesson development</p> <p>Exists as reference for learners after the workshop</p> <p>Potential for "dynamic" features, such as quizzes or other interactive material, or to capture cohort progress</p>	<p>Expertise required for/with hosting infrastructure</p> <p>With repository-based hosting (such as GitHub), repository expertise needed for developing materials</p>
Slides (via presentation)	Instructor-led, controls learning experience	<p>Hard to gauge learning effectiveness, particularly online</p> <p>Struggling learners left behind (mitigated somewhat by ample time and opportunity for questions)</p>
Training videos	<p>Requires no instructor effort to deliver</p> <p>Easily rewound or revisited (compared to live delivery)</p>	High effort to produce, update, and maintain
Printed handouts	Some learners prefer a physical medium	<p>Not practical for long courses</p> <p>Not environmentally friendly</p>

Once the materials are in a functional state, and ideally long before their pilot, invite colleagues external to the training materials development team to review them. A fresh perspective on the material will help spot potentially fundamental errors and obstacles to learning that are missed during development due to expert awareness gaps or being "too close" to the material. Where possible, invite reviews from two different types of reviewer:

- **Those with similar prerequisite skills to the target learners**, i.e. what are the learning obstacles, what needs clarification, what works well and what needs improvement from a learner perspective
- **Those with knowledge and experience of the training topics**, i.e. suggest ways to simplify the taught techniques, identify missed and valuable learning opportunities that should be included, and prioritise parts to be removed based on their practical value (which is useful if the material is known to be too long)

How to Promote a Pilot?

Promoting your pilot workshop effectively is crucial to attracting the right participants and ensuring a successful event.

To maximise your chances of reaching your target audience, consider using a variety of advertising channels. You could reach out to groups who have previously attended your training sessions and send targeted emails to mailing lists that are relevant to the workshop's subject matter. You could also post adverts in relevant Slack channels used by your target audience and include information about your workshop in newsletters that reach your potential participants.

Start promoting the course well in advance to ensure there is enough time for participants to learn about the workshop and sign up. Begin advertising the workshop as soon as the details are confirmed and send out promotional information multiple times to increase visibility. Something to remember is that promotion isn't a one-shot activity, so as the date approaches, consider sending reminder emails to potential participants.

Your promotional materials should be clear, concise, and informative. It's useful to include the following key points:

- **Workshop topic:** provide a brief introduction to the subject matter, especially if the topic is not widely known.
- **Course level and prerequisites:** specify the level of the course (novice, intermediate, advanced) and any prerequisite knowledge. Consider including a short form or quiz to assess participants' current knowledge.
- **Location:** indicate where the course will be held. If online, mention the platform (e.g., Zoom, Microsoft Teams). For in-person pilots, indicate whether the venue can accommodate certain accessibility requirements. If the venue has not yet been determined or could be changed, ask participants about their accessibility requirements when they sign up.
- **Dates and times:** clearly state the workshop dates and times.
- **Eligibility:** specify who the course is open to (e.g., students from a particular university).

- **Instructors and delivery method:** introduce the instructors and outline the method of delivery.
- **Expectations:** set clear expectations regarding what will be taught, how it will be delivered, and that learner feedback is expected.
- **Registration process:** explain what will happen if too many people sign up. Indicate whether it's first come, first served or if there will be a selection process.

When creating your advert, aim for brevity while ensuring it contains all necessary information. Keep the advert short and to the point, ensuring key details are prominent – for example, make critical details like the date, time, and topic bold and large. Alternatively, keep the advert short but provide a link to a more detailed explanation of the workshop - perhaps on an event website - for those who need more information.

Strategically promoting your workshop through various channels, starting early, and providing clear, concise information all help to attract the right participants.

How to Deliver a Pilot?

How to Staff a Pilot?

From the teaching side, in addition to instructors who teach the course, you may want to consider having helpers who, whilst not involved in class teaching, assist learners with any issues or questions. Instructors often adopt the role of helper when not instructing. It's generally recommended to have a ratio of learners to helpers of between 1:5-1:10, depending on the course and how it's delivered. Helpers work particularly well with in-person courses, or those held online with the cohort separated across different virtual rooms (e.g. 5 learners per room with 1 helper in each); in both cases helpers are able to address issues with a minimum of crosstalk. They are less effective with online instructor-led courses however, since issues can't be vocally discussed without interrupting the instructor. Complex issues may be resolved in separate virtual rooms, although it becomes much easier for the learner to fall behind. Smaller issues can be resolved over text chat.

Helpers do not necessarily need to come from within the internal training team. For courses delivered to learners within a singular discipline, recruiting helpers from the same discipline who have applied the taught techniques is very effective. Groups that request training for their less experienced members may well have experienced staff happy to act as helpers throughout the course.

Counterintuitively, instructors who are not experts in the subject matter can be an excellent choice for novice courses, especially if they learnt the topic or skill recently. This is because their obstacles to learning the topic, and how they overcame them, are still fresh in their mind and can be applied to their teaching. Conversely, there's a tendency for experts to suffer from an "expert awareness gap", where their own struggles in learning the fundamentals are long forgotten and so are harder to appreciate, especially if they haven't taught the topic before. For less experienced instructors, short informal practice teaching sessions with co-instructors boosts confidence and helps identify areas for improvement.

How to Schedule a Pilot?

Scheduling a pilot workshop requires careful planning and flexibility to accommodate potential issues and gather valuable feedback.

Before the workshop begins, consider organising a pre-pilot software installation surgery, particularly if installation is complex. This session allows learners to ensure all necessary software is installed correctly on their devices and to familiarise themselves with the new software and tools that will be used during the workshop. It also provides an opportunity for learners to speak directly with instructors and resolve any technical issues. This preemptive step can prevent delays and disruptions on the first day of the workshop.

It can be helpful to allow larger time margins during a pilot workshop to handle unexpected delays without rushing through the content. This is particularly important on the first day where unforeseen technical challenges are most likely to occur. For example, you could start early on the first day to allow for extra time setting up and addressing any last-minute technical issues and have extra helpers available at this time to help with troubleshooting.

Consider scheduling half-day sessions rather than full-days for a pilot workshop. This approach gives you the chance to tweak materials between sessions if necessary and to make course corrections based on feedback and observations from the previous session. Half-day sessions also reduce the intensity of the workshop, making it easier for both learners and instructors to stay focused and engaged. Additionally, learners are likely to retain new information more effectively if the content is spread over multiple days.

Pilots can be more taxing than regular workshops for both learners and instructors. To ensure everyone remains attentive, schedule regular breaks throughout the sessions to prevent fatigue and maintain concentration. The instructors could also encourage participants to stretch, hydrate, and step away from their screens during breaks.

How to Run a Pilot?

Delivering a pilot workshop effectively requires careful planning, clear communication, and adaptability.

First, let's consider the introduction to the workshop. You can enhance your workshop introduction with a few key elements to set yourself up for success in the rest of the workshop. Start by having the instructors and helpers introduce themselves. This initial interaction increases the likelihood that learners will engage throughout the workshop. From the start, establish an upbeat and exciting tone to create a positive and energetic learning environment. If the workshop will be long or cover difficult content, prepare learners for the challenge and remind them of the benefits of mastering the subject matter. Clearly indicate which aspects of the training are being piloted and which are well-established and emphasise the importance of receiving feedback from the learners on the piloted aspects of the workshop. In the introduction, it's also useful to inform learners about the break schedule for the workshop so they can plan their time accordingly.

Throughout the workshop, regularly check in with the group to gauge the pace and give learners the opportunity to ask questions, and adjust the speed of the course as needed to ensure everyone is keeping up and note any questions or problems that arise. This feedback provides valuable insights for improving the materials and delivery in future sessions. If the workshop is instructor-led, consider sharing the delivery between multiple instructors. This approach helps keep the energy high and gives each instructor a rest. Make sure you adhere to the break schedule announced at the beginning, since this helps learners manage their time and maintain focus.

As this is a pilot workshop, it's likely that not everything will go to plan. When something goes wrong, it's helpful to remember that this is the purpose of pilots. If appropriate and feasible, you could work with the learners to solve the problem in real time, or make notes of the issue

so that you can fix it before the next workshop. It can be particularly helpful to identify and connect with learners who tend to encounter issues first. These "advance party" learners can help identify problems before the larger group is affected, and provide an opportunity to resolve or mitigate issues before they become larger problems experienced by the wider group. Encourage them to report issues promptly and consider offering incentives for their feedback.

Overall, when delivering a pilot workshop:

- **Encourage interaction:** keep the atmosphere interactive to foster engagement and create a dynamic learning experience.
- **Provide clear instructions:** make sure instructions are clear and concise to minimise confusion.
- **Be adaptable:** be prepared to adapt your plan based on real-time feedback and observations.
- **Collect feedback:** continuously collect feedback throughout the workshop to refine and improve the content and delivery for future sessions, and ensure that the participants understand the importance and value of filling in the post-workshop survey.

Post-workshop Activities

It's worth remembering that, particularly for a pilot, the workshop isn't complete as soon as it's been delivered. In order to get the most out of a pilot workshop, aim to collect and action as much useful feedback as possible. This can be done in a number of ways.

Firstly, in terms of the surveys:

- **Don't neglect asking any attendees who dropped out early to fill in the survey**, since otherwise your survey analysis is subject to survivorship bias, and it's important to understand why the training didn't connect with anyone who did not see it through to the end .
- **Analyse results from post-workshop survey ability questions against the same results in the pre-workshop survey**, which will help to understand the extent to which learning took place across the pilot, and helps to highlight training material areas that need improvement. For example, if learning effectiveness for a particular training episode was low, this may highlight issues with the content, its delivery, or its portrayal in the material. This analysis also provides evidence on the impact of these workshops which can be used to support funding of these activities in the future.
- **Collate and analyse survey text responses for areas of success and improvement.** This helps direct future improvement work and any positive comments provide qualitative support for the activities. Consider requesting longer testimonials from attendees who particularly liked the training, to publish in blog posts or future promotional material, for example.
- **Consider a follow-up with attendees**, perhaps between 3-6 months after the pilot, to ask how useful they have found the training in their work and any areas that were particularly valuable.

Having feedback from attendees is only one side of the feedback coin, so it's also important to obtain feedback from the training team. One way to do this is to hold a debrief (also sometimes referred to as a "retrospective" or "post-mortem"), where aspects of organisation, delivery and materials can be discussed to identify successes and areas of improvement from the perspective of the trainers. It also provides an opportunity to quickly prioritise issues and potentially assign them to individuals and schedule the remedial work.

10 Key Points

- **Prioritise early planning and preparation for the training.**
- **Be specific about what aspects of a training workshop you are piloting**, and how you'll collect feedback on each of them.
- **Consider and select how the training will be hosted and delivered carefully**, taking into account the nature of the training material and the learners.
- **Ensure you build sufficient "margins" into the schedule**, to account for any unforeseen challenges which are typical for a pilot.
- **Set expectations with learners**, for the need for learner feedback as well as learning outcomes.
- **Make it easy for both attendees and the training team to supply feedback** and have it recorded, since it's easy during busy training sessions to fail to record key findings.
- **Use post-pilot reflective sessions** with trainers to highlight areas for improvement and assign tasks so failings aren't repeated.
- **Ensure enough time and effort for the training team to make improvements** to the materials prior to subsequent training events.
- **Prioritise improvements that will have the most benefit now** and leave other improvements for a later pilot, particularly if you have limited effort.
- **Accept that pilots will not always be as successful as you hope**, which is really the point of pilots, to work out what works and what doesn't, and what needs to improve. It's about the identification of issues to avoid repeating them in the future, and more than that, about adopting a mindset of continuous improvement; one that can be taken forward in all training events. So in a way, every training event is a pilot!